

CEE2ACT

**Empowering the Central and
Eastern European Countries to Develop
Bioeconomy Strategies and Action Plans**

D3.2 Establishment of the National Bioeconomy Hubs

Funded by
the European Union

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1. Executive summary

The purpose of this document is, first and foremost, to present documentation and verification of the establishment of ten National Bioeconomy Hubs ('Hub') of the CEE2ACT project, one in each of the CEE2ACT target countries. It first provides a definition of the National Bioeconomy Hub and explains the aims of the Hub and their role that they play in the project (chapter 2). In chapter 3, the standardised structure of the online presence of the Hubs is outlined. Chapter 4 gives a brief summary of each Hub's first workshop in terms of focus and participating stakeholders. The URL to the webpage of each Hub is provided. Observations and next steps for the Hubs is summarised in chapter 5. Finally, the agendas of each Hub workshop can be found in the annex (chapter 6).

DISCLAIMER

The CEE2ACT project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2. Aims of the National Bioeconomy Hubs

Transitioning to a circular economy, including circular bioeconomy, is needed to reduce the use of raw resources and materials and to reduce the environmental impact of our current economy and business models. A circular bioeconomy offers a sustainable economic model that shifts resource use from non-renewable sources to the use of biomass that can be regenerated. In this context, national strategies play a key role in fostering the transition to a circular bioeconomy and improving resource management.

The CEE2ACT countries in Central and Eastern Europe currently lag behind other European countries in the development of such national strategies and action plans (European Commission, 2021). The need to develop a national strategy becomes even clearer considering that many private entities in the CEE2ACT countries are already engaged in bioeconomy activities, highlighting the untapped potential in these countries' bioeconomy. Developing a national strategy makes it possible to adapt the principles of a circular bioeconomy to country-specific characteristics and needs, unlocking new opportunities for business innovation in the country. To improve the effectiveness of a national strategy, it is crucial to engage different stakeholders in strategy development to ensure the inclusion of diverse views, interests and needs.

To this end, a National Bioeconomy Hub ('Hub') was established in each of the ten CEE2ACT countries. The Hub is a platform that brings together key relevant stakeholders such as businesses, ministries, public administrations, civil society organisations and research institutes through workshops, training sessions, forums, and other activities, that foster exchange of ideas and common elaboration of national bioeconomy roadmaps. The Hubs are led by national coordinators that run activities that support Hub members in contributing to the circular bioeconomy transition in their countries. They are built on existing networks and clusters, and are being supported by e-solutions such as inventories of best practices, e-learning modules, self-assessment tool, B2B matchmaking tool, and methodology for developing bioeconomy strategies and action plans.

Figure 1 shows how the Hubs will be used throughout the project and gives an overview of a series of workshops that will be conducted in each of the 10 countries implementing the Hubs:

How do we achieve our mission?

Figure 1 CEE2ACT Workshop series vision for each National Bioeconomy Hub

Hubs were established in month 14 of the project (October 2023) and will run until the project ends. However, they do not necessarily have to be limited to the project lifetime if partners and Hub members are motivated to continue working together within the Hub framework. If the foundations for trust, cooperation and collaboration can be established during the project, it would be beneficial to use these even beyond the project lifetime to further the transition towards a circular bioeconomy.

3. Online structure

Each of the ten Hubs has a dedicated online presence via the CEE2ACT website (see Figure 2).

The webpage design, information display per sub-section and consultations with all CEE2ACT partners took place during June-July 2023, which was a process led by the project leader in Communication and Dissemination (G!E). The webpage structure was completed by 10 September 2023, before the 3rd project meeting in Zagreb, which took place on 19 September 2023.

Hubs

Figure 2 Links on the project website to each Hub page

Each Hub page has the following information:

- Name, e-mail address, and website of the Hub coordinator;
- Summary of the current status of the national bioeconomy in the country;
- An overview of the most relevant biomass sources;
- An overview of the most relevant stakeholder groups involved in the Hub; and
- Past and upcoming events.

CEE2ACT Home News and Events Affiliates Hubs Resources Tools Contact

Poland

CEE2ACT HUB COORDINATOR AND CONTACT PERSON
 Name: Piotr Jung
 E-mail: piotrjung@polski.pl
 Web: www.polski.pl

BIOECONOMY STRATEGY
 Several Ministries are developing elements of a bioeconomy strategy, but there is no single institution/entity that can bring those parts together and coordinate the development of a bioeconomy strategy at national level.
 There is also work being done at regional level to prepare a bioeconomy strategy, e.g. for the Mazowieckie Region. Other regions include bioeconomy elements in their Regional Innovation Strategies (e.g. Świętokrzyskie or Lubelskie).
 Most of the regions have set out in their strategies areas of smart specialisation related to the bioeconomy, such as biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, environment, biomedical products, biomedical biotechnology, etc.

CHARACTERISTICS
Biomass sources:

- Agricultural crop residues
- Wood and forestry residues
- Livestock waste
- Industrial waste from agri-food industry
- Food waste
- Inland fisheries residues
- Industrial waste from wood products industry

STAKEHOLDERS AND MINISTRIES INVOLVED IN THE NATIONAL BIOECONOMY HUB

- National policy makers (Ministries)
- Regions and regional policy bodies
- Rural development agencies
- Customers
- SMEs
- Universities and research centres
- Technology parks and regional incubators
- Innovative start-ups
- Financial institutions
- NGOs and civil society
- Environmental organisations
- Farmer organisations

WORKSHOPS AND EVENTS

- [Bioeconomy Conference in the Polish Senate](#)
- [Kick-off meeting for the National Bioeconomy Hub on 3-4 October 2023](#)

MORE INFO AND EXTERNAL LINKS
 More info coming soon.

CONTEXT AND CONNECTIONS
 The national bioeconomy hub brings together representatives from different bioeconomy sectors, focusing initially on agricultural biomass. By collaborating, the representatives of the biomass value chains support the development of a bioeconomy strategy, develop business models and jointly perform activities to develop the bioeconomy. The development of the hub follows recommendations and best practices in projects such as BioEcon (H2020) or BIOEASTUP (H2020).

Figure 3 Webpage of Polish national bioeconomy hub

As the members of the Hubs are progressively increasing after the organization of the 1st National Stakeholder workshops, the information about members of the hubs will be uploaded in a sub-section of the webpage of each Hub.

The hub coordinators will make sure that the information of the members is updated thoroughly and throughout the project duration.

Also, the Hub coordinators will continuously search for potential new members of the hub and encourage key national bioeconomy stakeholders to become members regardless of their participation in the 1st national bioeconomy workshop.

The information displayed on the CEE2ACT website about each member of the hub per country, will depend on the specific institutional conditions of each organization.

4. Establishment of National Bioeconomy Hubs

The Hubs were established as planned by month 14 of the project (October 2023) and were officially launched through the first national workshops. A brief summary of each Hub workshop can be found in this chapter.

i. Bulgaria

The [Executive Forest Agency](#) – CEE2ACT Hub coordinator based in Bulgaria – held the first CEE2ACT national workshop on 22 June 2023. Representatives of science, business, branch organizations and the administration gathered at the first working meeting to discuss the possibilities and potential for the development of the bioeconomy in our country. The event was initiated by the Forestry Executive Agency as a partner in the implementation of the project "Assisting the countries of Central and Eastern Europe in developing strategies and action plans for the bioeconomy" - CEE2ACT under the "Horizon Europe" program of the European Union.

Eng. Miroslav Marinov, Deputy Minister of Agriculture and Food, and Eng. Valentin Chambov, chairman of the working group, who took part in the discussion, expressed full support for the work of the expert group. The event was opened by Eng. Stoyan Toshev, executive director of IAG, who emphasized the importance of the topic and wished for successful realization of the set goals.

The focus of the talks outlined the need to engage all stakeholders in the creation of a national vision and the identification of priorities and strategic goals for the development of the bioeconomy, which would lead to the preparation of a road map for the development of a National Strategy and a corresponding action plan.

The participants in the meeting are categorical about the need for a national document for the development of the bioeconomy in the country, in which, based on the cross-sectoral approach, the needs, national goals, priorities and actions are clearly defined. They will contribute to more efficient use of bioresources, creation of higher added value, new jobs, increase of knowledge and capacity of employees in individual sectors, economic, social and environmental sustainability in their management.

The meeting was attended by representatives of the Ministry of Energy (ME), Ministry of Innovation and Growth (MIR), Ministry of Economy and Industry (MII), Ministry of Agriculture and Food, South Central State Enterprise, Sofia University SU "KI. Ohridski", Agricultural University - Plovdiv, Forestry University, Institute of Forestry at BAS, Executive Agency for Forestry, Executive Agency for Fisheries and Aquaculture (IARA), Branch Chamber of the Woodworking and Furniture Industry (BKDMP), BULPROFOR - Branch Association of Forestry Practitioners and Forest Entrepreneurs in Bulgaria, the National Biomass Association, the National Association of Non-State Forest Owners "Gorovladelets", the companies "Kronoshpan", "Svilotsel", "Mondi Stamboliyski".

Picture 1. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in Bulgaria

The webpage of the Bulgarian Hub can be found at:
<https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/bulgaria/>

ii. Croatia

In the next two years, the Croatian National Bioeconomy Hub - coordinated by [WWF Adria](#) - in cooperation with the Ministry of Agriculture, will work on monitoring the implementation of the National Bioeconomy Strategy, designing new projects and facilitating the joint cooperation of key stakeholders to exchange information, knowledge and experience.

The Minister of Agriculture, Marija Vučković, also supported the establishment of the Hub, whose Ministry led the drafting of the strategy. At the same time, she emphasized that the goal of the strategy is to ensure the strengthening of the economic sectors in the bioeconomy.

Figure 4 Minister of Agriculture (L) with CEE2ACT coordinator (R) at the 1st Hub meeting in Croatia

On 20 September, the launch event gathered representatives of many institutions such as the Ministry of Agriculture, the Croatian Chamber of Agriculture, the Ruđer Bošković Institute, the Hrvoje Požar Energy Institute, the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Shipbuilding, the Faculty of Food Technology in Osijek, the Faculty of Food Technology of the University of Zagreb, the Institute for development and international relations, the Association of Cities of the Republic of Croatia, and civil society organisations.

Figure 5 Snapshot of the 1st Hub meeting in Croatia

More information on the Croatian Hub launch can be found at: <https://www.cee2act.eu/wwf-adria-launches-the-bioeconomy-hub-in-croatia/>

iii. Czech Republic

The [Czech University of Life Sciences](#) (CZU) launched the CEE2ACT Czech Bioeconomy Hub in Prague on 26 September 2023. The hybrid workshop was attended by 11 external participants, including representatives from the Ministry of Environment, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, the BIOEAST HUB, the Czech Technology Platform for Biofuels, the National Cluster Association, the Municipal Water Management Company, relevant companies and researchers in forestry.

The fruitful discussion among participants focused on the current state of bioeconomy development, especially obstacles related to the implementation and the terminology in strategic materials. Bioeconomy stakeholders explored possible synergies between CEE2ACT and other international projects including better outreach of the project.

Picture 2. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in the Czech Republic.

The webpage of the Czech national bioeconomy hub can be found at: <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/czech-republic/>

iv. Greece

[CluBE](#) launched the Greek National Bioeconomy Hub on 10 September, during the 87th Thessaloniki International Trade Fair. The Hub is bringing together diverse stakeholders in an open dialogue discussion focused on the present state and future possibilities of bioeconomy in Greece.

The workshop primary objective was clear: unite stakeholders from different sectors – government, academia, and industry – to foster collaboration in research and development, innovation, and commercialisation of bio-based products and services. One of the significant outcomes of the workshop was the affirmation of the Greek Bioeconomy Forum’s pivotal role in the operation of the Hub. This forum will mobilise companies and institutions. The participating stakeholders, a diverse group ranging from agricultural product providers to academic institutions and government ministries, form the backbone of this initiative.

As Greece takes these strides towards a bio-based future, the collaborative spirit exhibited at the CEE2ACT workshop and the establishment of the National Bioeconomy Hub stand as testaments to the nation’s commitment to innovation, sustainability, and a prosperous future. Through unity and shared vision, Greece’s bioeconomy is set to flourish, paving the way for a greener, more sustainable future.

Picture 3. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in Greece.

The webpage of the Greek national bioeconomy hub can be found at: <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/greece/>

v. Hungary

[Geonardo](#) was pleased to host the first CEE2ACT National workshop on 5 October 2023. This event, generously supported by Európa Pont (Representation of the European Commission in Hungary) gathered a diverse group of 21 participants from various sectors, who are influential stakeholders in Hungary’s bioeconomy ecosystem. During

the workshop, Geonardo reminded the audience about the CEE2ACT objectives connected to the establishment of the CEE2ACT national hubs.

In the case of Hungary, the Hungarian Bioeconomy Forum is an inclusive platform that welcomes individuals and entities possessing expertise, experience, and knowledge in the field of bioeconomy, including projects, organisations, institutions, policymakers, SMEs, investors, research institutes, societies, conservation bodies, and more. This “format” of the Hungarian Hub was an alternative solution was developed to avoid duplication of efforts on gathering relevant bioeconomy actors and evade division of the already established organizations working on sustainable circular bioeconomy.

The CEE2ACT project allies and partners, including the Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking presented their work in bioeconomy, and exciting discussions covering stakeholder needs and bioeconomy policy topics took place.

Picture 4. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in Hungary.

The webpage of the Hungarian national bioeconomy hub can be found at: <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/hungary/>

vi. Poland

A meeting inaugurating the Polish national bioeconomy hub was held at the headquarters of [IUNG-PIB](#). At the invitation of IUNG-PIB, the PRO CIVIS Foundation for Education and Social Dialogue and EPRD Biuro Polityki Gospodarczej I Rozwoju Regionalnego Sp. z o.o., nearly sixty representatives of almost forty entities from all over Poland gathered in the Czartoryski Palace hall. Among them were representatives from the scientific community, business, non-governmental organisations, business community institutions, and regional and state administration.

In addition to the intensive two-day conference that included panel discussions and working group debates, participants also formulated their expectations and needs for the future Hub.

Picture 5. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in Poland

The webpage of the Polish national bioeconomy hub can be found at: <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/poland/>

vii. Romania

The official launch of the National Bioeconomy Hub in Romania, and the first working session with the stakeholders took place on 26 September 2023, in Sfântu Gheorghe, Romania, with a total of 35 participants. It was hosted by the Bioeconomy Incubator and organised by our CEE2ACT partner – the [Association of Small- and Medium Size Enterprises of Covasna County](#) (ASIMCOV).

Most of the participants are stakeholders involved in bioeconomy since 2019, innovation clusters such as Green Energy Innovative Biomass Cluster, AgrooFood Regional Cluster, ProWood Cluster, Transylvania Textile&Fashion Cluster, Department of Sustainable Development, Regional Development Agency Centru, but representatives of SMEs, universities and civil society were also present.

Participants shared their experiences related to bioeconomy, then synergies with other similar projects were identified and ideas for long-term collaborative initiatives were outlined. The main conclusion of the event was that there are solid

partnerships that need to be developed continuously in order to outline a national vision regarding the national bioeconomy strategy.

The Sustainable Development Department in Romania is one of the major stakeholders of the Bioeconomy Hub, and has the role of maintaining permanent contact with the ministries (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forest, Ministry of Economy, Entrepreneurship and Tourism, Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization), and ensuring their involvement in the development of the national bioeconomy strategy.

The event was registered as a side event of the European Sustainable Development Week ([ESDW](#)).

Picture 6. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in Romania.

The webpage of the Romanian national bioeconomy hub can be found here: <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/romania/>

viii. Serbia

The establishment of the Serbian Bioeconomy Hub and first CEE2ACT workshop took place on 6 October 2023 in Belgrade, Serbia. The Serbian Hub is coordinated by the [Institute of Forestry](#) (IOF). A total of 29 participants attended the workshop. Twenty-one

stakeholders from 20 different institutions were present, including decision-makers in the creation and implementation of policies, public administrators, actors in the primary sector of the economy, the waste sector and the bio-based industry, small and medium-sized enterprises, public enterprises, suppliers of raw materials, scientific research and educational institutions and organisations for environmental protection.

The workshop was attended by representatives of Ministry of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia, Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Serbia, Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Serbia – Forest Directorate, Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia – Center for Circular Economy, Chamber of Commerce of Serbia – Association for Plant production and food industry, Chamber of Commerce of Serbia – Association for Forestry, Wood Processing, Furniture and Paper Industry, Public Enterprise “National Park Fruška Gora”, Public Enterprise “National Park Kopaonik”, Public Enterprise “National Park Tara”, Public Enterprise “Srbijašume” “, Faculty of Forestry, University of Belgrade, Institute for the Application of Science in Agriculture, Institute for Plant Protection and Environment, WWF Adria, Regional Agency for the Development of Small and Medium Enterprises Alma Mons, Guarantee Fund of AP Vojvodina, Cirekon doo, Eko Bio Invest doo, Foresting doo and Mercator-S doo.

The Institute of Forestry based in Serbia received positive feedback from all participants, who were very willing to participate in the further work of the Serbian Bioeconomy Hub.

Picture 7. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in Serbia.

The webpage of the Serbian national bioeconomy hub can be found at: <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/serbia/>

ix. Slovakia

On 18 October 2023 in Nitra, the Slovak Bioeconomy Hub was officially established. The event, organised by the [Bioeconomy Cluster](#), gathered more than 50 participants from various organisations, including policy, academia, R&D, and practice, which can be considered as key stakeholders of the Slovak bioeconomy ecosystem. The programme fostered discussions about the bioeconomy in Slovakia and its opportunities. Competent representatives of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development informed participants about the status of work on the strategic Roadmap.

The CEE2ACT project and its tools were presented to the participants, alongside possibilities for synergies and cooperation with other bioeconomy initiatives. During the presentation of the best practices, a new material, NonOilen® was showcased. It was developed in Slovakia; it is 100% biodegradable, and the presence of its creator stimulated many debates regarding its practical use and concrete ideas for the future. The youngest generation was not forgotten either – the programme included the selection of the best picture from the exhibition installed in the premises of the Institute of Knowledge Agriculture and Innovation. Children drew their stories, and the most beautiful story will go to the international round, organised by the FAO.

Picture 8. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in Slovakia.

The webpage of the Slovakian national bioeconomy hub can be found at: <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/slovakia/>

x. Slovenia

[Anteja ECG](#) launched the Slovenian Bioeconomy Hub through a collaboration between the CEE2ACT Project (Anteja) and Bioloc Project (Združenje kemijske industrije), on 12 October 2023.

During a lively workshop, 20 participants revealed interesting findings and discussed the challenges and opportunities in the bioeconomy in Slovenia.

Specifically they addressed the following topics:

- Most promising new value chains in Slovenia,
- Opportunities in bioeconomy for the young generations (marginalised groups), and
- Financial challenges and opportunities in implementing circular technologies

Picture 9. Snapshot from the 1st Hub meeting in Slovenia.

The webpage of the Slovenian national bioeconomy hub can be found at: <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/slovenia/>

5. Observations and next steps

The ten countries targeted in CEE2ACT have in common the fact that they do not have a national bioeconomy strategy yet. However, they differ widely in the stage they are currently at in terms of developing a national bioeconomy strategy or action plan: in some countries, the term '*bioeconomy*' is not at the forefront of political discussions, while in others there is a ministry charged with developing such a strategy and working

groups have been formed for this purpose. Similarly, there is a variance in the strength and activity of existing bioeconomy engagement initiatives, as well as the ease of cooperating with them. For example, CEE2ACT partners in Slovakia and Greece are well-connected and central to engagement activities with other bioeconomy actors in the country, making it easier to find synergies, while in the Czech Republic and Hungary, negotiations with existing hubs and clusters have been more challenging as CEE2ACT partners try to find ways not to repeat existing work or create a parallel process.

One of the main next steps for each Hub is to plan the second national workshop to build knowledge and capacity of stakeholders for the development of bioeconomy strategies. In the meantime, it is crucial that Hub coordinators continue to facilitate discussion and cooperation with – and between – Hub members to contribute to the transition to circular bioeconomy in CEE countries.

6. Annexes

1. Agenda – 1st workshop – Bulgaria

Time	Topic
11.00-12.00	Arrival
12.00 -12.45	Lunch break
12.45-13.15	Registration and opening
13.15-13.30	Welcome to the participants by the eng. M. Marinov - deputy. Minister, eng. Stoyan Toshev - Executive Director, eng. V. Chambov - Director of Southwest forest enterprise - Blagoevgrad
13.30 – 14.20	Presentation - "Development of the bioeconomy in Bulgaria, existing sectoral and regional policies in the field of the bioeconomy" - PhD. eng. L. Trichkov, project coordinator
14.20-14.45	Discussion on the state of play and possibilities for the development of the bioeconomy. The bioeconomy in the partner countries of the CEE2ACT project - videos about the experience of the partners, their best practices - Daryana Manova, PR expert on the project
14.45-15.15	Presentation - Project "Assisting the countries of Central and Eastern Europe in developing CEE2ACT bioeconomy strategies and action plans", work packages, goals and objectives, progress (with emphasis on WP 3 and the need of a National Bioeconomy Hub) - PhD. eng. Nestor Domuschiev, expert WP 5 of the project

15.15-15.40	<p>Discussions:</p> <p>Proposals for a vision with identified priorities and strategic goals for the development of a National Strategy in Bulgaria. Presentation of the previously identified priorities/strategic objectives, summarized in order to form the thematic subgroups.</p> <p>Perspectives and possibilities, The opportunities to sign a memorandum of cooperation and understanding between the stakeholders - PhD. eng. L. Trichkov - project coordinator</p>
15.40-16.10	Coffee break and interviews with the Working group participants
16.10-17.00	Discussion and the final composition of the thematic subgroups.
17.00-17.30	Organizational issues related to the thematic subgroups and the Working group future activities

2. Agenda – 1st workshop – Croatia

Agenda	
09:30-10:00	Registration and welcome coffee
10:00-10:15	<p>Opening remarks</p> <p>Nataša Kalauz, CEO WWF Adria Marija Vučković, MSc, Minister of Agriculture (TBD)</p>
10:15-11:00	<p>Bioeconomy in Croatia – Status and Projects in Croatia</p> <p>Anita Sever-Koren, Director General for Agriculture Policy, EU and International Affairs: Development of Bioeconomy Strategy in Croatia</p> <p>Sofija Babić, Policy Officer, WWF Adria: CEE2ACT Project – The Role of National HUB in Development and Implementation of Bioeconomy Strategy in Croatia</p> <p>Presenting Bioeconomy Projects in Croatia (tour de table)</p>
11:00-11:30	<p>Bioeconomy in CEE2ACT Contributing Partner Countries</p> <p>Videos</p>
11:30-11:45	Coffee break
11:45-12:30	

	<p>HUB Development and Knowledge Transfer from CEE2ACT Partners</p> <p>Hilke Bos-Brouwers and Marcela Viquez Zamora, Wageningen University: Knowledge Transfer in Developing Projects between Research Institutions and Private Sector Ioannis Fallas and Giorgios Martinidis, CLUBE: Stakeholder Cooperation on HUB Launch and Bioeconomy Initiatives in Greece Mateja Novak, Anteja: Circularity Approach in Developing Strategy in Slovenia</p>
12:30 – 13:00	Discussion of HUB members on future steps and workshops
13:00	Lunch and networking

3. Agenda – 1st workshop – Czech Republic

Time	Topic	Speaker
9:30-10:00	Welcome coffee	
10:00-10:10	An introductory word	Miroslav Hájek
10:10-10:25	CEE2ACT Project overview and objective and other similar projects, establishment of the Bioeconomy Hub	Miroslav Hájek
10:25-10:45	The current state of the bioeconomy in the Czech Republic and bioeconomy at the regional level	Eva Cudlínová
10:45-11:00	Experience with bioeconomy strategy abroad	Petra Palátová

12:15-12:50	Discussion on the issue of bioeconomy in the Czech Republic	
12:50-13:00	Conclusion and next steps	Miroslav Hájek

4. Agenda – 1st workshop – Greece

Time	Topic	Speaker
10:45-11:00	Welcome coffee Arrival & welcome, opening	Ms. Angeliki Foutri, CluBE

11:00-11:15	CEE2ACT Project overview and objective, bottom-up approach and building the Greek Bioeconomy Hub	Dr. George Martinidis, CluBE
11:15-11:30	The status and prospects of Bioeconomy in Greece, the Greek Bioeconomy Forum as a cornerstone of development	Ms. Elena Anthi, Greek Bioeconomy Forum
11:30-11:45	A best practice case: how CluBE promotes bioeconomy in Western Macedonia	Dr. Yannis Fallas, CluBE
12:00-12:40	Round table / open dialogue on the future prospects and needs of bioeconomy in Greece	
12:40-13:00	Q&A, CEE2ACT and Hub next steps and how to join	Ms. Angeliki Foutri, CluBE

5. Agenda – 1st workshop – Hungary

WHEN?	WHAT?	WHO?
09:00-09:15	Welcome coffee Arrival & welcome, opening	GEO
09:15-09:45	Project overview and objective, bottom-up approach and preliminary results. Hungarian Bioeconomy Cluster and synergies with CEE2ACT and bioeconomy projects	GEO, Bay Zoltan Nonprofit Ltd, project representatives
09:45-10:15	Evaluating the current state and future prospects of Hungary's bioeconomy	MoA
10:15-11:00	Panel session The journey to bioeconomy (bioeconomy example setting). Hungarian Bioeconomy Stakeholders and their experiences in the bioeconomy sphere.	Private sector representatives
11:20-11:55	New bio-based value chains and good practices - the experience from CEE2ACT contributing partners. Biomass use and waste valorisation.	CEE2ACT partner-contributing countries
11:55-12:10	Fostering bioeconomy in Central Eastern Europe	CBE JU representative, TBC
13:10-14:20	Roundtable session: How to move the Hungarian bioeconomy forward? Bioeconomy needs in Hungary.	Discussion led by GEO & CEE2ACT contributing partner representative, all participants
14:25-14:30	Q&A, CEE2ACT next steps & wrap up	GEO team

6. Agenda – 1st workshop – Poland

Informal part

10.30 – 12.00	Meeting at the Kepa farm - field demonstration of the work of the autonomous robot (for those willing / interested)
12.00 – 13.00	Guided Tour in Puławski Park or visit the laboratory section - INCBiR IUNG-PIB
13.00 – 14.00	Lunch before the event

Launch of the National Bioeconomy Hub

14.00 – 14.15	Opening of the meeting - Director of IUNG
14.15 – 14.30	International cooperation and the role of consulting in the development of the bioeconomy - EPRD Biuro Polityki Gospodarczej i Rozwoju Regionalnego Sp. z o.o. and Fundacja Pro Civis

Panel "Consequences of climate change and the role of the bioeconomy" (chaired by Dr Jerzy Kozyra)

14.30 – 14.40	Consequences of climate change - Dr Jerzy Kozyra IUNG-PIB
14.40 – 14.50	The role of biogas and biomatene in mitigating climate change - Prof. Dr. Jacek Dach
14.50 – 15.00	The role of micro-organisms in reducing the impact of drought - Sławomir Gacka, ProBiotics Polska
15.00 – 15.30	Discussion panel
15.30 – 15.45	Coffee break

Panel „Finansowanie biogospodarki” (prowadzenie dr hab. Grzegorz Siebielec)

15.45 – 16.00	Horizon 2024 - NCP - (Ms Bożena Podlaska)
16.00 – 16.15	LIFE Programme / Mr Andrzej Muter (National Fund for Environmental Protection in Warsaw)
16.15 – 16.30	Cooperation programme - support under the new Rural Development Programme / p. Anna Goldys, Agricultural Innovation Team for the operation of the SIR, Agricultural Advisory Centre in Brwinów Branch in Warsaw
16.30 – 16.45	Discussion

Panel "The concept of bioeconomy development through added value" (moderated by Prof. Mariusz Matyka, PhD)

16.45 – 16.55	Support for the development of business models in soft fruit production - Dr Łukasz Kopiński Ribes Technologies (start-up representative)
16.55 – 17.05	Cascade extraction of biomass as an opportunity to increase its added value – Chair of InnEco Ltd.
17.05 – 17.15	Vertical farms as a new model for bioproduct production - Dawid Drzewiecki, Vertigo Farms
17.15 – 17.25	Innovative business model in carp and trout production - Anna Pyć / PUSTELNIA Sp. z o.o.
17.25 – 17.35	The role of biocompost in increasing the added value of biomass - Tomasz Wojciechowski, Chairman of GWDA Piła Sp. z o.o.
17.35 – 18.00	Panel discussion
18.00 – 18.15	Coffe break

Summary

18.15 – 18.30	The need for a strategy for bioeconomy development - support for ongoing projects - Piotr Jurga (IUNG), Damian Kuznowicz (EPRD, PRO CIVIS)
18.30 – 18.45	Concept of a National Bioeconomy Hub - Piotr Jurga (IUNG), Damian Kuznowicz (EPRD, PRO CIVIS)
18.45 – 19.10	Discussion
20.15	Gala Dinner (Sybilla Restaurant / Puławy)

7. Agenda – 1st workshop – Romania

Time	Topic	Speaker
10:00-10:15	Press conference - Local, regional and national media representatives	Mr. Miklos Levente Bagoly, Mr. Lajos Vajda
10:15-10:30	Registration of participants - Welcome coffee	
10:30-10:45	Opening speech	Mr. Miklos Levente Bagoly, president Mr. Laszlo Borbely
10:45-11:45	CEE2ACT – project overview goals, expected outcomes, National bioeconomy HUB – purpose and objectives , stakeholders involvement	Ms. Maria Gaspar,
12:00-13:30	Roles to be assumed by the stakeholders in the development of the hub – Cooperation with other EU projects in the field of bioeconomy - Be-Rural, AgroBioHeat, BioRural, RuralBioUP	Mr. Lajos Vajda, director
13:30-14:00	Q&A, wrap up session	Mr. Miklos Levente Bagoly, president
12:00-13:30	Roles to be assumed by the stakeholders in the development of the hub – Cooperation with other EU projects in the field of bioeconomy - Be-Rural, AgroBioHeat, BioRural, RuralBioUP	Mr. Lajos Vajda, director
13:30-14:00	Q&A, wrap up session	Mr. Miklos Levente Bagoly, president

8. Agenda – 1st workshop – Serbia

Time	Session	Speakers
09:30 10:00	Registration and Welcome Coffee	
10:00 10:10	Welcome and Introduction	Dr Ljubinko Rakonjac , Institute of Forestry Dr Nevena Čule , Institute of Forestry
10:10 10:20	CEE2ACT in focus: Project overview, goals, expected outcomes and preliminary results	Dr Nevena Čule , Institute of Forestry
10:20 10:50	Bioeconomy in focus: Definitions, scientific consensus, prospects, and the status in Serbia	Dr Ilija Đorđević , Institute of Forestry Prof. dr Jelena Nedeljković , University of Belgrade, Faculty of Forestry Prof. dr Zorica Sredojević , University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture
10:50 11:00	National Bioeconomy Hub in focus: Overview, purpose and objectives, Importance of stakeholder engagement, Insights gained from initial stakeholder meetings	Dr Ljiljana Brašanac-Bosanac , Institute of Forestry
11:00 11:40	Stakeholders in focus: Experiences and Roles in the Circular Bioeconomy	Aleksandra Vučinić , Ministry of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia Ivana Putnik , Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia - Center for circular economy Milica Vračević , Regional agency for the development of small and medium size enterprises Alma Mons d.o.o., Novi Sad Milan Veselinov , CirEkon d.o.o.
11:40 12:00	Coffee Break	
12:00 12:40	Contributing countries in focus: Best practices from CEE2ACT Contributing Partners	Elisabeth Schmies , BOKU, Austria Kalle Aro , LUKE, Finland Felix Schumacher , CSCP GmbH, Germany Paula de la Sen , CIRCE, Spain Dr Hilke Bos-Brouwers , WUR, Netherlands

Time	Session	Speakers
12:40 13:10	Building trust through collaboration: Interactive session for Expertise and Resource Sharing	All participants
13:10 13:15	Q&A, CEE2ACT next steps & wrap up	Institute of Forestry
13:15 14:15	Networking Lunch: Extending Conversations about the Bioeconomy Hub	

9. Agenda – 1st workshop – Slovakia

12.00 – 13.30	Lunch / Networking
13.30 – 14.00	Registration of participants
14.00 – 14.10	Opening and welcome – Bioeconomy Cluster and its contribution to bioeconomy ecosystem <i>Katarína Blicklingová, Bioeconomy Cluster</i>

14.10 – 14.20	Bioeconomy best practice example – 100% biodegradable material NonOilen® <i>Pavol Alexy, PANARA s.r.o.</i>
14.20 – 14.30	Roadmap for circular bioeconomy – state of the art <i>Peter Kuric, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic</i>
14.30 – 14.40	CEE2ACT and its support to Slovak Bioeconomy Hub <i>Dana Šimová, Bioeconomy Cluster</i>
14.40 – 15.00	Synergies with other initiatives, perspectives of cooperation (BIOEASTsUP, BOOST4BIOEAST) <i>Dana Peškovičová, National Agricultural and Food Centre</i>
15.00 – 15.10	Inspiration from Europe – Netherlands <i>Video from partner – Wageningen University</i>
15.10 – 16.00	Discussion: Bioeconomy in Slovakia and how to benefit from it <i>Moderator: Daniel Ács, Bioeconomy Cluster</i>
16.00 – 16.30	Coffee and open discussions

10. Agenda – 1st workshop – Slovenia

WHEN?	WHAT?	WHO?
08:30-09:00	Welcome and Registration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants arrive and register for the event. 	
09:00-09:15	Introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome remarks from the organisers, including an introduction to the CEE2ACT project and its objectives, as well as the BIOLOC project and its objectives (<i>Mateja Novak makes the remarks for CEE2ACT and Alenka Dovč for BIOLOC</i>) Introduction to GZS and Anteja collaboration (<i>GZS will provide the network of stakeholders and use its expertise in connecting stakeholders while Anteja will provide with technical expert knowledge and further consultation if needed</i>) Introduce the concept of the National Bioeconomy Hub and its role in fostering collaboration and circular projects (<i>we want to scale up 3 projects in Slovenia, consulting companies and forming new consortiums</i>) 	Mateja Novak, Alenka Dovč

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A brief overview of the day's agenda and objectives. 	
09:15-09:25	Introductory speech - Mateja Dermastia Anteja ECG - consulting for the transition to a circular bioeconomy	Mateja Dermastia
09:25-09:45	Setting the Context <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation on the importance and potential of circular bioeconomy for all the interested sectors. • Highlight the key challenges and opportunities in transitioning to a circular bioeconomy in Slovenia (<i>NLB bank - 500 million for green investments, presentation of circular business models that work, examples of success from abroad - insects in France, biochar in Switzerland and alternative meat in Switzerland - projects are being done, so what is stopping Slovenia? This will be discussed in the workshop</i>) 	Miha Škrokov
10:00-10:15	Workshop Introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the purpose and goals of the upcoming workshop (<i>finding their pains and challenges</i>) • Provide an overview of the workshop structure and expected outcomes (<i>we want to write down where you need help the most to offer the best services through the hub</i>) 	Miha Škrokov, Alenka Dovč
10:15-11:30	Identifying Industry Pains and Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate a brainstorming session where participants share the main challenges they face in transitioning to circular bioeconomy practices. • Use of sticky notes or a digital collaboration tool to collect and categorise the challenges (<i>either a whiteboard with sticky notes or a miro board if they have a projector – we will just write 6 different sections – policy, finding solutions, implementation, energy efficiency, whatever it may be on the wide board and then put stickers where they say they are interested in our help</i>) • Open the floor for a broader group discussion, allowing participants from different workshops to share insights and cross-pollinate ideas. • In the end, present potential solutions, identify key actors, and discuss the steps needed to implement circular bioeconomy projects to show Antejas approach on actual case studies. 	Miha Škrokov, Alenka Dovč, Mateja Novak
11:30-12.00	Wrap-up and Next Steps <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summarise the key takeaways from the workshop and group discussions and show the most pressing problems from the workshop. • Emphasise the importance of collaboration and cooperation in driving circular bioeconomy initiatives. • Introduce the follow-up activities and how participants can get involved in the National Bioeconomy Hub's ongoing projects (<i>tell the date of the first workshop and what the theme will be</i>). • Distribute relevant materials, contact information, and any additional resources (<i>bring the penguins and the flyers and everything else</i>). 	Mateja Novak, Alenka Dovč